

RECREATION OF ANCIENT HYDROTECHNICAL STRUCTURES SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of recreation of ancient hydrotechnical structures in Uzbekistan and their geographical location.

Key words: Recreation, Hydrotechnical facility, North Nurota-Tomdi tectonic fault, Koshrobot-Ariston regional tectonic fault, water reservoir, kulkakli pond, hot water, koriz, kugush, mining ditch, mashaldon, pond, Kimsan, Attor, Labi Pool.

Recreation is one of the current issues of geography. This problem can be solved by geographical research of ancient hydrotechnical structures in some regions. Narshakhi (1991, p. 106), Nasir Khysrav (2003, p. 96), Sh.Shomuhamedov (1963, p. 34), L.I. Rempel (1981, p. . 110), V.I. Kochedamov (1957, p. 165-186)' G. A. Pugachenkova (1951, p. 48), U. Alimov (1984), D. A. Nozilov (1997, p. 14) such authors emphasize. Although it has been shown in Chapter II of this work that some devices included in the series of hydrotechnical structures have a recreational value, it should be noted that the recreational value of ponds, lock ponds, canals, and ditches is also extremely important. Their service in this regard is especially exaggerated on the scale of large cities. For example, we noted that there were more than a hundred pools in the city of Bukhara until the beginning of the 20th century according to the information of the Institute of Tropical Medicine (Rempel, 1981, p. 146). In fact, it turns out that their number is several times more than the indicated numbers. Because the names of Kimsan, Attor, Labi Hovuz and several other unnumbered structures are not found on the map mentioned above. But the existence of these large and small water bodies and their role in moderating the microclimate to a certain extent cannot be denied. Therefore, the recreational importance of ponds begins to show itself. In the example of the city of Bukhara, the geographical distribution of the pools is as follows. Pools that form a whole ensemble, combined with the administrative buildings of the city. Gavkushon (XVI century), Hovuzi Nav (XVII century), Labi Hovuz (XVI-XVII centuries), Nadir Devon Begi (XVII

century) v. h. These waterworks were more crowded with mudarris, scholars of knowledge, and were their favorite recreation centers. A number of rare architectural monuments such as Nazar Elchi, Nadir Devon Begi, Qazi Latif, Domullo Sher, Ibrahim Okhun madrasa surrounding the ponds were overflowing and created great excitement among vacationers and voters (Rempel, 1981, p. 66). . Some of them, for example, the Labi Pool monument, are still of great importance for Bukharians and local and foreign tourists who come to see the city, precisely from the point of view of recreation. Around dozens of pools, such as Mir Do'stim, Dost Chirog, Khoja Zayniddin (16th century) made of stone, which are part of residential areas, teahouses and sheds for recreation have always been favorite places of recreation for residents. On the days of Eid, people used to fill the cool couches by the ponds to enjoy the art of bakers, pastry chefs, cooks, morboz, gatekeepers, entertainers, wrestlers, and hafiz. Many people know very well that vacationers will not be spared the size of all city, village and neighborhood pools of Uzbekistan even without holidays. Pools such as Bahovuddin Naqshbandi, Saifiddin Boharzi, Chor Bakr, Hazrat Imam (XV-XVI centuries) formed a whole ensemble with the houses of famous sheikhs, religious scholars, saints, and these structures have played the role of recreation centers for pilgrims. In particular, marble pools, which are part of the Bahovuddin Naqshbandi and Chor Bakr monuments, played an important role in the recreation of vacationers and volunteers, and some of them have not lost their importance in this regard.

Pools that are part of the magnificent gardens owned by big officials (khan, governor, qazi, etc.) - for example, the stone pool of Sitorai Mohi Khosa (XIX century), the luxurious swimming pools of Khan Chorbog, Mirzo chorbog, Zakotchi chorbog in Karmana served for the recreation of officials. . Small ponds, designed for individual families, are located in inner courtyards or gardens, surrounded by fruit and ornamental trees, and in the shaded areas of the trees for relaxation, one-foot-high sofas open up to a common view. . Even on hot summer days, the pool is distinguished by its considerable coolness, neatness and comfort to the vacationer, and because of this, it is valued as an important recreation area from ancient times to the present day, but their number is decreasing. It is difficult to imagine all the historical settlements of Uzbekistan, like the villages and towns of all arid lands, without canals. It is the simplest philosophy that mankind has always settled on the banks of water and improved that land with its work. While working, they rested by a cool stream or canal, sometimes to improve the quality of rest, they selected the most convenient places on the banks of that stream and canal, and created favorable conditions for recreation. Therefore, such places are recognized as the most convenient place for public gatherings, holidays, parades, and weddings due to their popularity. Siyokhob (Buorasuv) in the city of Samarkand, Obi Mashhad ditches, on the eve of Navruz holiday, Kazan was full", "It became rich", "Gunoh tokildi", along with ancient ceremonies and rituals, folk dances and celebrations were held (History of Samarkand, 1971, 43 -page): It is known that not only Samarkand, but also the

canals of Tashkent city such as Bozsuv, Qanqus, Khichqiriq, and the banks of Bukhara city such as Joygozi, O'tror, Qalandarkhana, Gulobiyan, Zarminok, Bogdosh, Foshun, Laylak, were built for people's leisure purpose. There were even special experts who made chorbog. For example: Mirak Said Ghiyos built a beautiful garden for Ubaydullah Khan in Bukhara (D. Nozilov, 1997, p. 14).

In fact, Bukhara has been famous for the freshness of its streams and canals since ancient times. In the 10th-11th centuries, Molyon stream became extremely famous in this regard. There was no better place and destination in Bukhara than the beautiful paradise-like status of Joyi Moliyan (Joy, Juy in Persian means stream, channel, A.N.). Because all its places were covered with palaces, gardens, flower gardens and bostons. It is provided with constant flowing water (stream, canal, A.N.). His meadows were connected to each other, and streams flowed between them in a thousand directions to meadows and flower gardens. Everyone who watched the flowing waters wondered where this water was coming from and where it was going. This is how the masters of their time drew. All the land from Registan Square to Dashtak was full of tall houses, decorated with stone, decorated with various pictures, beautiful ponds and good drinking pools. In Sada, the rocks took the form of a tent in such a way that the sitting place on the edge of the lake did not get a single ray of sunlight either from the east or from the west (Narshakhi, 1991, p. 106). This brief opinion about the resting place on the bank of the river named Joyi Molyon indicates that in the 10th century, the banks of canals, ditches, and ponds around the city of Bukhara were the most comfortable places for vacationers.

However, the fact that canals, ditches, and ponds have become the center of people's leisure activities, folk fairs, and festivals has not been excluded from the way of life. According to G.A.Pugachenkova (1951, p. 48), U.Alimov (1984), the importance of recreation of ancient hydrotechnical structures increased especially in the Middle Ages. The periods of strong statehood (XIV-XVI centuries), especially during the period of Amir Temur, Shahrukh Mirzo, Mirzo Ulug'-bek, Abdullah Khan II, the establishment of many parks are famous in large settlements such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Karmana, Shahrisabz, Nasaf, Termiz, Tashkent and their surroundings. gardens were built on the banks of ancient hydro-technical structures. People did not even think of going far to satisfy such a need due to the availability of recreation in the areas close to their places of residence. In our time, due to the rapid growth of the population, the problem of choosing the right recreation areas is becoming more urgent. Because the movement of recreation areas towards the upper parts of natural water sources complicates the issue. Recreational areas cause pollution of natural basins. In our study of the author of these lines, "Hydrological bases of the selection of recreation areas in karst areas" (A. Nizomov et al., 2004, p. 35), the fourth and fifth order base surfaces for

recreation areas are recognized as the most promising. When we compare the results of this research with the recreation areas associated with ancient hydrotechnical structures, we can see that ancient architects solved the problem very effectively. Because our generations have sharply limited the polluting factor of flowing water bodies, therefore their upstream, that is, the main source, has been kept clean. Only some very small water facilities, such as a swimming pool, are compatible with the upper, that is, third-order base surfaces. It is also important to note that the ponds have no or very little polluting effect on the environment. Even so, it can be observed that the recreation value of ponds, ditches, canals, such as ponds, ponds, and canals has significantly decreased in our time. Nowadays, it is necessary to increase the importance of recreation of ancient hydrotechnical structures. Because through this event, we will protect the upper parts of our rivers, which are considered ecologically clean, from the "attack" of vacationers. As a result, the natural condition of running water sources is somewhat improved.

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